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Statistical Modelling and Upscaling of Firebrand Generation from Structural Fires

Final Report

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ABSTRACT

Firebrands are small fragments of hot material that are lofted and transported by a fire plume and wind, and when landing nearby can ignite other materials. To understand the hazard that firebrands pose to the surrounding environment, their generation must be characterised across scales from laboratory experiments to full-scale experiments, including the distribution of firebrand sizes and masses generated by a fire. While firebrand generation behaviour in wildfires has been widely studied, the generation of firebrands from fires across building structures remains a significant yet underexplored hazard, despite numerous instances where building-to-building ignition has been observed to be instigated by firebrands. This study analyses experimental data discovered from the literature and develops a comprehensive model to predict firebrand generation from structural fires. The current literature highlights fuel moisture content, wind, structural geometry and material, and heat release rate of fire (HRR) as key factors in firebrand generation. A statistical characterization of the mass and projected area of generated firebrands was conducted, identifying a log-normal distribution most effectively characterise these variables. Due to the absence of full-scale experimental data in the literature, correlations for firebrand generation in wind tunnel experiments were upscaled to full-sized building experiments through non-dimensionalisation. In 500 iterations of this model, the number of firebrands generated was predicted to have an average value of 3981 ± 72 , representing 3.4 % of the initial fuel mass. This was a 7.2 % increase from the observed firebrand count in a previous building fire experiment, indicating the model's reasonable accuracy. Furthermore, larger firebrands were predicted in the model than in the experiment, which have a higher ignition potential but a shorter travel range. Limitations in the experimental data, which were biased towards smaller and less dense firebrands collected post-transport and post-burning, affect the accuracy in predicting firebrand transport and ignition potential. The developed model supports the conclusion that upscaling results from laboratory experiments can provide a valuable prediction for full-scale experiments and enhance fire mitigation in urban settings.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract.....	ii
Acknowledgements.....	iii
Table of Contents	iv
Nomenclature	v
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background	2
1.2 Objectives.....	4
1.3 Structure of Report.....	4
2 Current Literature on Firebrand Generation.....	4
2.1 Research Gaps.....	9
2.2 Summary	9
3 Experiments in Firebrand literature	10
3.1 Log-Normal Distribution	12
3.2 Firebrand Yield.....	13
4 Scaling Analysis.....	14
4.1 Scaling Methodology	16
4.1.1 Assumptions.....	17
4.1.2 Mean Mass Prediction	20
4.1.3 Bivariate Log Normal Distribution	21
4.1.4 Validation.....	23
4.2 Scaling Results	23
4.2.1 Predicted Mean Mass and Mean Projected Area	23
4.2.2 Generation of Firebrand Samples	25
4.2.3 Model Validation.....	27
4.2.4 Sensitivity Analysis.....	28
5 Further Discussion	31
6 Conclusion.....	33
7 References.....	34
Appendix A.....	37
Appendix B.....	41

NOMENCLATURE

A	Projected area of firebrands (m^2)
A_s	Surface area of the initial fuel (m^2)
b	Power law exponent
β	Slope of the line of best fit (g/cm^2)
C_p	Specific heat capacity of air ($J/kg \cdot K$)
g	Gravitational acceleration (m/s^2)
H	Ejection height of firebrands (m)
HRR	Heat release rate of fire (W)
m	Mass of firebrands (kg)
N	Number of firebrands generated
r	Pearson correlation coefficient
R	Radius of firebrands (m)
T_0	Absolute Ambient Temperature (K)
U_v	Maximum vertical airflow velocity induced by the plume (m/s)
U_∞	Ambient speed condition (m/s)
V	Volume of firebrands (m^3)
W^*	Non-Dimensional Firebrand Number
y	Yield of Firebrands
λ	Mean parameter of log normal distribution
μ	Mean
ρ	Density (kg/m^3)
σ	Standard deviation
ζ	Standard deviation parameter of the log-normal distribution

1 INTRODUCTION

When fires occur outdoors, buildings can ignite through direct flame contact, thermal radiation, or firebrands, either individually or in combination. Direct flame contact involves a structure touching flames from nearby burning materials, while thermal radiation from hot objects can ignite nearby fuels based on their proximity and exposure time [1]. On the other hand, firebrands can ignite structures at a greater range of distances. Firebrands are small fragments from wood or non-combustible, lofted by a fire plume that can ignite other materials. These firebrands, upon landing on flammable materials can trigger ignitions and cause subsequent fire to spread via direct flame contact and thermal radiation.

Numerous studies have conducted empirical and experimental research to understand the conditions under which firebrands are generated in wildland fires, including thermomechanical breakage mechanisms of firebrand breakage on a fractal tree [2][3], advanced computational fluid dynamics model to predict flight trajectories and landing patterns [4] and effects of vegetative tree species on firebrand generation. However, firebrands can also be generated from building structures (structural fires), presenting a significant yet underexplored hazard to urban areas. A notable instance of this is the spread of the Itoigawa-city fire, igniting 147 structures over 40,000 m² [5], and more recently scaffolding from a Hong Kong high-rise building ignited 6 nearby buildings [6], demonstrating the significant impact firebrands can have on urban fire spread. Figure 1(a) shows the fire spread in Itoigawa-city, while Figure 1(b) illustrates the smouldering firebrand embers generated in Hong Kong.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: (a) Fire spread in Itoigawa-city [7], (b) Hong Kong scaffolding fire [6]

This risk is amplified by trends toward sustainable urban development using engineered timber, which produces more firebrands than steel and concrete structures, necessitating the need for a predictive model of firebrand generation. While many global jurisdictions enforce legal mandates to minimize fire spread in buildings in wildland areas, current engineering methodologies in urban sites neglect the threat posed by firebrands. For this reason, it is important to investigate the mechanisms behind firebrand generation to protect structures from damage.

1.1 BACKGROUND

The development of firebrand is generally characterised with three stages: generation of firebrands, transport by plume lofting and ignition of fuel beds. This report will focus on the initial generation stage in structures, illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Firebrand generation, transport, and ignition processes showing a timber building compartment ignited and generating firebrands (adapted from Mitchell et al. [8])

Firebrands originate predominately from burning organic materials such as vegetation and wooden structures and detaching from their sources due to external forces such as drag force from wind and fire plume, or gravity, inducing stresses and moments [1]. Wood, being a cellulosic

material, undergoes pyrolysis at high temperatures, which involves the thermal degradation of organic material and the formation of gaseous products, leaving behind a layer called char. This char is a porous and brittle medium that can cause internal stresses that reduce the wood's surface density and stiffness, causing wood shrinkage and resulting in crack formation [9]. As the fire progresses, the temperature increase reduces the strength of wood. Subsequently, external loading caused by wind and fire plume causes the char layer to crack and eventually fall off [3]. Furthermore, delamination can occur when laminated layers in a timber element separate [10]. With varying extents of charring, cracking and internal stresses, firebrands of different shapes and sizes can be generated. An example of a structural wind tunnel experiment in Figure 3 (a) showing a corner assembly ignited with a T shaped burner and water pans downwind for firebrand collection. Firebrands generated are shown in in Figure 3 (b) Moreover, the morphology of firebrand fuels such as fuel moisture content (FMC), density, material, and geometry influences firebrand fuel generation.

Figure 3: (a) Experimental set up of firebrands generated from a wall assembly wind tunnel experiment, (b) firebrands generated, adapted from [11]

While modelling of firebrand generation from wildfires has been widely investigated, structural fires are difficult to model due to the lack of large-scale and comprehensive firebrand data in thick timber structures. Additionally, the process of structural firebrand generation is less understood and limits the potential for a physics-based model for structural firebrand generation.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this project is to develop a statistical and knowledge-driven model to predict firebrand generation in structural fires. This involves understanding firebrand generation mechanisms and lessons learned from wildfires as documented in literature and utilizing gaps and existing knowledge from the literature review to develop a comprehensive model. The project aims to analyse extensive wind tunnel test data to gain insights into firebrand generation patterns and behaviours. To create the firebrand generation model, statistical modelling with empirical correlations is employed. Given the absence of full-scale data in the literature, the project conducts scaling analysis from wind tunnel experiments to a full-scale building experiment. The model results are validated with data from a full-scale building experiment. Ultimately, the developed model will serve as an input in firebrand transport and ignition models [12], contributing to the probabilistic assessment of fire spread and supporting the design of safe and sustainable buildings.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF REPORT

This report is divided as follows. Section 2 details the current literature on firebrand generation, and research gaps that may impact the project going forward. Section 3 details firebrand generation patterns and behaviours that can be learned from wind tunnel firebrand generation data. Section 4 describes the upscaling process from the wind tunnel data to a full-scale assembly. Section 5 discusses the results of the wind tunnel and full-scale assembly. Section 6 concludes the report and highlights future development areas. The project was coded in python.

2 CURRENT LITERATURE ON FIREBRAND GENERATION

Current literature lacks understanding fundamental processes of firebrand generation in thick timber structures. Consequently, research on firebrand generation in vegetation is investigated and adapted to structural contexts.

Caton-Kerr, Tohidi & Gollner [9] proposed an initial framework of the process of firebrand generation through the thermo-mechanical breakoff model. This can be viewed in three phases:

thermo-mechanical instability at microscale, physiochemical degradation processes, and thermo-mechanical break-off due to external loading. These processes can happen simultaneously, or in stages as wood is burnt. In the thermo-mechanical break off process, macro-cracks form tangentially and micro-cracks longitudinally due to internal moisture content boiling and gas buildup, causing internal pressure and wood shrinkage. The second phase, physiochemical degradation process involves pyrolysis and oxidation, creating a porous char layer which allows oxygen transportation and burning. Oxygen reacts with the char to form carbon dioxide (CO_2) and carbon monoxide (CO) products and leaves an ash layer on the surface of the branch, reducing the diameter, wood density, and stiffness [13], illustrated in Figure 4. This process further propagates the existing cracks through the char layer. The final phase involves external forces like wind and gravity causing weakened branches to break off. As pyrolysis and oxidation occur, the reduction of diameter of branches eventually reaches a critical diameter, when it fractures at its attachment point [2].

Figure 4: Cross section of a branch or firebrand showing the char and ash layer

Timber elements have a rectangular, thick geometry that typically differs from thinner cylindrical branch components. In such geometries, corners tend to char more rapidly when exposed to fire

from two sides [14]. In addition, the weakening of a structure due to charring primarily occurs at the surface of the material. Hence, the branch fracture stress to generate fragments of burning firebrands is less relevant to a thicker structural wood geometry, but generation is characterised by the forces required for the char to fall off from the surface. Furthermore, mass timber buildings often incorporate engineered timber elements that are manufactured using multiple wood pieces bonded together with adhesives. A key difference between these engineered timber beams and wooden branches is their susceptibility to firebrand generation due to their laminated nature. Delamination, which involves the separation or splitting of layers, can significantly weaken the structural integrity of timber [10]. Such weakening can cause the failure of structural components and reduce the shear stress required to cause char fall off, and hence firebrand generation.

In a study by Tohidi, Kaye & Bridges (2015), statistical description of firebrand size and shape distribution was determined. In the study, drag was broken down as horizontal drag and vertical drag. The horizontal airflow was due to ambient winds, and the vertical airflow was induced by the heat release from fire. The maximum vertical airflow velocity is given Equation (1).

$$U_v = 2.45 \left(\frac{g^2 \dot{Q}}{\rho_{air} C_p T_0} \right)^{1/5} \quad (1)$$

Where \dot{Q} is the heat release rate of fire, ρ_{air} is the density of air, C_p is the specific heat of air, T_0 is the absolute ambient temperature. On the other hand, Himoto et al. [15] used the plume equation given as Equation (2), in a structural fuel experiment. Both equations involved the heat release rate which controlled the velocity experienced by firebrands. The limitation of this plume equation is that the ejection height (H) had to be measured in firebrand experiments. Furthermore, charring rates can be affected by fuel morphology: fuel moisture content (FMC) and density of material. Higher FMC and density generally result in larger masses of firebrands due to incomplete combustion [16][17].

$$U_v = \begin{cases} 6.83 \dot{Q}^{1/5} \left(\frac{H}{\dot{Q}^{2/5}} \right)^{1/2} & \text{if } (H < 0.08\dot{Q}^{2/5}) \\ 1.85\dot{Q}^{1/5} & \text{if } (H < 0.20\dot{Q}^{2/5}) \\ 1.08 \dot{Q}^{1/5} \left(\frac{H}{\dot{Q}^{2/5}} \right)^{-1/3} & \text{if } (0.20\dot{Q}^{2/5} < H) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

While research on fundamental generation process structural firebrand generation mechanisms is limited, considerable efforts have been made in collecting experimental data.

Investigations by Suzuki and Manzello explored wind-induced effects on controlled burns of a two-story full-scale structure and various structural assemblies, including corner assemblies and cedar siding treatments [18]. The studies found that higher wind speeds result in the production of thicker firebrands [19], shown in Figure 5. An increase in wind speed also resulted in heightened firebrand production. Wind tunnel experiments on structural firebrand generation revealed that the collapse of floors and roofs created strong updrafts, thereby facilitating the detachment of burning materials [20].

Figure 5: Comparison of firebrands under varying wind speeds, adapted from [19]

A report by Zhou, Quarles, and Weise [11] characterized firebrand size, mass, and traveling distance by burning structural assemblies, including fences, corners, and roofs, wall assemblies at different wind speeds. This study generated over 28,000 firebrands, measuring the mass and projected area of each firebrand, releasing the data in a public domain. This experiment provides the raw data used in the small-scale experiment in this report.

A chronological analysis by Yoshioka et al. [21] categorized firebrands into ash and charcoal types and investigated events that encourage firebrand generation during a fire's evolution, such as flashover and structural collapse. Video footage revealed a significant increase in ash-type firebrands post-flashover. The study found that wet pans collected six times more firebrands than dry pans, suggesting finer firebrands in dry pans were blown away or burned out.

Currently no studies have modelled the physical mechanisms of firebrand generation in structures. In vegetative firebrand generation, Barr & Ezekoye [2] developed a model based on the aerodynamic shear of structurally weakened branches, predicting firebrand generation when branches reach a critical flexural stress. Tohidi, Kaye, and Bridges [3] analysed firebrand size and shape distributions from trees, revealing that firebrand surface area scales with mass to the power of 2/3. Ju et al. [17] conducted scaling analysis to derive empirical correlations for firebrand yield (% of initial mass burnt) from Douglas Fir, Eucalyptus Globulus, and Coast Live Oak. They examined factors such as fuel moisture content (FMC) and crosswind speed, proposing a power law function linking firebrand yield to these variables given as Equation (3).

$$y_{firebrand} = FMC^a \left(\frac{U_\infty}{\sqrt{gD_{twig}}} \right)^b \quad (3)$$

To this date, there has been limited development in structural firebrand modelling. Current models for firebrand generation models primarily rely on statistical generation based on existing experimental data, with a notable lack of models incorporating the heat release rate (HRR) of fire. Himoto et al. [15] presents a methodology for estimating probabilistic models of structural firebrand generation and transport using a hierarchical Bayesian approach to compensate for limited data availability. The model was based on the projected area of firebrands released, estimating data from a full-scale burn of a three-story wooden building and wind tunnel experiment burning wood cribs. The model used dimensionless parameter of firebrand number, given as Equation (4) to integrate the small-scale and full-scale experimental data.

$$W^* = \frac{\rho_\infty U_v^2}{\mu_\rho gH} \quad (4)$$

The Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS), developed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), is a computational fluid dynamics model designed for simulating fire-driven fluid flow using a large eddy simulation approach. Wickramasinghe et al. [4] presented a methodology combining experimental data with FDS to determine firebrand generation rates using inverse analysis to reproduce the firebrand landing distribution from a single tree and a forest fire. However, data scarcity limited result validation.

2.1 RESEARCH GAPS

There are several research gaps highlighted throughout the literature review. With the key gap being the understanding and modelling of firebrand generation in thick timber structures and engineered timber beams. Additionally, existing models on timber beam charring focus on the mass loss from timber beams, but not the actual process of char fall off and firebrand generation. This limits the potential for a physics-based model for structural firebrand generation. Although there is existing data on the mass and projected area of firebrand generation, there is a lack of integration between the heat release rate of an actual urban fire in empirical models that link firebrand characteristics. This is crucial for predicting firebrand generation according to the conditions of fire. This lack of integration stems from the lack of heat release data with firebrand characteristics available. This limitation restricted the project model to statistical modelling as physical processes have not fully been investigated and physical processes cannot be validated.

2.2 SUMMARY

The study of firebrand generation from structural fires presents a complex process that encompasses thermodynamics, material science, and environmental factors. The current literature highlights fuel moisture content, wind speed, structural geometry, material density, and heat release rate of fire (HRR) as key factors in firebrand generation. Structural firebrand generation is less researched, and the distinct behaviour of thick timber beams, especially engineered timber, underscores the need for specialized research in this area. The examination of experimental studies and firebrand modelling reveals progress yet highlights the necessity for

more advanced models that incorporate heat release rates and thick timber elements. This limited physical modelling approaches for this project. Consequently, a statistical modelling approach was employed using data from wind tunnel experiments conducted by Zhou et al. [11]

3 EXPERIMENTS IN FIREBRAND LITERATURE

In this section, the methodology and characterisation of mass and projected area of firebrands generated from burning wall mock-up assemblies in wind tunnel experiments collected by Zhou et al. [11] are detailed. These experiments were referred to as ‘small-scale’ throughout the project. Experiments were conducted in a large open-jet wind tunnel. In total, 30 experiments were conducted with 10 different wall assemblies under 3 different wind speeds (5 m/s, 11 m/s, or 22 m/s). The wall assemblies were made of either cedar, oriented strand board (OSB), or fibre cement. Each wall in the assemblies used southern yellow pine framing, with a gypsum board attached to the non-fire-exposed walls. Gypsum boards are widely used in construction in fire-rated wall assemblies due to their fire-resistant properties. Several assemblies also contained combustible or non-combustible sheathing used to serve as a protective layer. Additionally, the samples were conditioned in a kiln to reach a moisture content of 5%.

Firebrands are characterised by the mass and shape as this determines the burning area and ignition potential of firebrands. Water filled aluminium pans were placed downwind of the burning components and firebrands are collected, oven dried, weighed, and placed under a camera to measure the projected area, illustrated in Figure 3. Often, there are unaccountable firebrand masses that have burnt out before landing on a water pan or are too small to be weighed. An initial exploratory data analysis was conducted to determine the probability distribution of firebrands, and to spot noticeable trends. A scatter plot was plotted, and outliers were identified, potentially due to measurement errors. Consequently, a filter was applied to remove incorrect measurements based on the physical limitations of the firebrands. The generated firebrand must have a projected area (A), mass (m) and density (ρ) less than the initial fuel material. Additionally, since the density of firebrands were not measured in the experiment, the firebrands were

assumed to be spherical in shape and the density was determined using the volume of a spherical firebrand (V) in Equation (5).

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V} = \frac{3m\sqrt{\pi}}{4(A)^{3/2}} \quad (5)$$

Where m is in kg, A is in m^2 and ρ is in kg/m^3 . Summing the firebrand count in 30 experiments, the total number of measured firebrands was 24104, and filtered firebrands was 12. The resulting range of density was 31- 53 kg/m^3 , significantly lower than the initial densities of cedar ($\sim 470 \text{ kg/m}^3$), OSB ($\sim 640 \text{ kg/m}^3$) and fibre cement ($\sim 1050 \text{ kg/m}^3$). This highlights the charring phenomenon as described in literature, where firebrands have a significantly lower density than the original fuel due to pyrolysis forming a porous char layer. Shown in Figure 6 is the scatter plot of the firebrands generated in 30 experiments, each point representing a single firebrand.

Figure 6: Scatter plot of mass vs projected area of cedar, OSB and fibre cement assemblies, raw firebrand data from [11]

It can be observed from the scatter plot that firebrands generated were concentrated in the lower mass and projected area range. The firebrands exhibited a linear relationship between mass and projected area. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was determined to quantify the variance of the linearity. The r value can be between -1 and 1, where the closer the magnitude of r is to 1, the greater the linear correlation of data. The range of r values was 0.875 – 0.969, indicating a

good and positive linear correlation. Additionally, the gradient of the line of best fit (β) was found by using the least squares method, given in Equation (6). Where A_i and m_i is the projected area and mass of the i -th data point. The intercept was set to 0 as the mass and projected area cannot be negative physical parameters.

$$\beta = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i \cdot A_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \quad (6)$$

3.1 LOG-NORMAL DISTRIBUTION

Analysing the probability of different sized firebrands through histogram distribution plots is important in determining the ignition potential of firebrands. Large firebrands have greater ignition potential, but are difficult to be lofted, whereas smaller firebrands can travel further distances and ignite structures from afar. Hence, characterising the probability distribution function (PDF), mean, and standard deviation of firebrand size can aid in determining the hazard posed by firebrands. As the linear relationship between mass and projected area was highlighted in Figure 6, only one parameter was fitted in a PDF, as the other parameter will have the same distribution. The projected area was selected for fitting as it can be measured with the assistance of machine learning algorithms, making the measurement less labour intensive.

Four common probability distribution functions (PDFs) were investigated: the normal, log-normal, exponential, and truncated normal distributions. For distributions with a small mean, the normal distribution contained negative values. Hence, the truncated normal distribution was also investigated, where negative values were set to 0 and the distribution was scaled to ensure the probability summed to 1. Shown in Figure 7 is an example PDF and histogram of a cedar assembly with combustible sheathing at low wind speed (5 m/s).

The results show that the normal and truncated normal distributions overpredicted firebrands in the mid-range (0.4 cm² to 0.6 cm²) and performed poorly at the extremes. The exponential distribution significantly overpredicted small firebrands (< 0.1 cm²) and did not capture the peak at ~0.1 cm². Observations of the 30 experiments show that the log-normal distribution was the most fitting PDF, capturing the right skewness of the histograms, but tend to overpredict small

firebrands than large firebrands. The log-normal distribution probability density equation is given in Equation (7), where x is the mass or projected area, λ is the log transformed mean, and ζ is the log transformed standard deviation.

$$\text{Lognormal}(x | \lambda, \zeta^2) = \frac{1}{x\zeta\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\ln x - \lambda)^2}{\zeta^2}\right) \quad (7)$$

Figure 7: PDFs and histogram of cedar assembly, low wind speed, raw firebrand data from [11]

3.2 FIREBRAND YIELD

The yield of firebrands (y) in this project is defined in Equation (8). The yield of firebrands was proposed as a function of fuel moisture content (FMC) and a combination of crosswind forces of drag and gravity [17] found in the literature. In this experiment, the FMC was kept constant, hence only effects of wind forces on the yield of firebrands were investigated. Shown in Figure 8 is cedar, OSB and fibre cement assembly with combustible sheathing at varying wind speeds.

$$y = \frac{\text{Total firebrand mass generated}}{\text{Initial fuel mass}} \quad (8)$$

The results indicate that as wind speed increased, the firebrand yield increased for all 30 experiments, a phenomenon similarly observed in literature [20]. The firebrand yield is also shown to increase linearly for all 30 experiments. Notably, the fibre cement assembly exhibited the lowest firebrand yield. At wind speed of 5.36 m/s, cedar had a firebrand yield approximately 5 times higher than fibre cement, and the yield from OSB was 3 times higher. As fibre cement is

non-combustible, it is less prone to firebrand generation. However, fibre cement lacks the sustainability benefits of timber materials like cedar and OSB.

Figure 8: Bar chart of wind speed against firebrand yield showing as wind increased yield, raw firebrand data from [11]

Additionally, OSB generated more firebrands under high wind speed conditions than cedar, whereas cedar generated more firebrands in the low wind speed category. This difference can be due to the lower density characteristic of cedar ($\sim 470 \text{ kg/m}^3$) compared to OSB ($\sim 640 \text{ kg/m}^3$), leading to easier ignition which can lead to a higher firebrand yield at low wind speed. At higher wind speeds with more aggressive burning, firebrands generated from cedar may burn out during transportation before it is collected.

4 SCALING ANALYSIS

While the complexities of actual firebrand behaviour can be simulated with full-scale experimental results, they demand significant time and resources. Upscaling laboratory experiments is crucial in understanding firebrand generation phenomena. Experiments by Suzuki and Manzello [22] have demonstrated that laboratory and full-scale assemblies exhibit similar characteristics, i.e. following a linear trend in mass and projected area, with wind speed significantly affecting both. Hence, correlations in small-scale laboratory experiments were

upscaled to full-scale building fires to understand the firebrand generation phenomena and is important for developing accurate predictions of firebrand generation to feed into the transport model.

This section outlines the methodology and results of upscaling the wind tunnel experiment conducted by Zhou et al. [11] against a full-scale 3 storey building firebrand experiment conducted by Hayashi et al [23]. This model employs a combination of physical and statistical methods to upscale wind tunnel experiments, which has not been done in current literature. Figure 3a shows the experimental set up of [11], while Figure 9 shows the experiments of [23].

Figure 9: (a) Full-scale firebrand experiment of 3 storey wooden building, (b) firebrands ejected

The model framework is shown in Figure 10 which outlines the process of upscaling from small-scale experiments to full-scale, where blue denotes small- scale and orange denotes full-scale.

Figure 10: Firebrand generation model framework

Considering physical parameters that influence firebrand generation is a more reliable approach to model firebrand generation (deterministic approach). However, often not all influential parameters are known. A statistical based approach on the other hand, can capture the stochastic phenomenon of firebrand generation. Hence, a combination of deterministic approach and statistical approach was combined in this model.

4.1 SCALING METHODOLOGY

The conditions of the wind tunnel and full-scale experiment is summarised in Table 1. The heat release rate (HRR) is a critical factor in firebrand generation as noted in literature, characterising the fire scenario. The maximum velocity as experienced by a firebrand is induced by a fire plume (U_v), which is controlled by the intensity of the fire. The plume induces a vertical velocity as the heat released by fire causes airflow to become buoyant and rise, which can initiate char-fall off and crack propagation. This was estimated with Equation (1) [3]. This plume velocity estimation was used Equation (2) used in Himoto et al. [15] as the equations required ejection height of firebrands which was not measured in the small-scale experiment.

Table 1 summarises the parameters of the full-scale and wind tunnel experiments.

Table 1: Full scale and Wind Tunnel Experiment Experimental Parameters

	Building Experiment (Full-scale) [23]	Wind Tunnel (small-scale) Experiment [11]
Fire Source	3 storey wooden building burnt in an open field	Wall mock-up assemblies, burned with natural gas burners
Material	Larch, pine wood, cedar, with gypsum board/ plasterboard finish	30 different wall assemblies of Cedar, Oriented Strand Board (OSB), and Fibre Cement
U_∞	4.6 m/s	5 m/s, 14 m/s, 23 m/s
A_s	2580 m ² (estimated)	1.21 m ²
HRR	257 MW (estimated)	0.05 MW
Initial Mass	~308,000 kg	~12 kg
U_{max}	22.5 m/s	4.07 m/s

N	4290	24104 (all experiments)
ρ_f	76 - 86 kg/m ³	31- 53 kg/m ³
A_p	0.364 – 65.4 cm ²	0.126 – 232 cm ²
Location of collection	49 - 670 m downwind of the fire source	Water pans up to 17 m downwind of the fire source

Where U_∞ is the ambient speed condition, A_s is the surface area of the initial burning fuel, N is the number of firebrands generated, ρ_f is the density of firebrands and A_p is the projected area of firebrands.

4.1.1 Assumptions

To ensure results between the wind tunnel and full-scale assemblies are comparable, there were numerous assumptions made:

1. The density of the firebrands generated between full scale and wind tunnel was assumed to be constant
2. Experimental conditions between the full-scale and wind tunnel experiments are similar.
3. Firebrands generated are assumed to have a spherical shape.

From Table 1, the firebrand density was higher in the full-scale assembly than in the wind tunnel. This is due to the higher heat release rate in the full-scale fire (257.2 MW) compared to the laboratory scale (0.05 MW). This higher heat release leads to more material combustion, pyrolyzing smaller firebrands into gases, and creating a stronger updraft due to increased thermal buoyancy. When more material is combusted, there is a significant amount of fuel supply and insufficient oxygen, resulting in incomplete combustion and lofting of partially charred firebrands with higher density. Despite these differences, there are no studies on the changes in fire scenarios, characterised by the HRR, affect firebrand density. Therefore, the density of firebrands was assumed to be the same in both wind tunnel and full-scale fires (assumption 1). Additionally, the full-scale assembly material was made of larch, pine, and cedar, whereas the cedar assembly in the wind tunnel experiment was made with cedar and southern yellow pine, with both assemblies finished with a gypsum board. As the density ranges of larch, pine, and cedar

overlap significantly, and the combustion characteristics for these woods are comparable, the intensity and behaviour of the fire in generating firebrands are assumed to be similar. Furthermore, the ambient wind condition in the full-scale assembly was 4.6 m/s, which is close to the in the low wind speed category (5m/s) of the laboratory data. Hence, the experimental results were deemed satisfactory to be upscaled to the full-scale assembly.

Lastly, as the firebrands generated was an input to the transport model, which assumed the firebrands to be spherical [12], this model also assumed firebrands were spherical. Firebrand Non-Dimensional Number

To generalise wind tunnel experiments for predicting full-scale firebrand generation, Himoto et al. [20] derived a non-dimensional firebrand number (W^*) by taking a force balance of gravity and buoyancy flow above the fire source. This was expressed as Equation (4). For this analysis, the ejection height was not measured during the wind tunnel experiment. Instead, it was deemed more appropriate to scale the non-dimensional firebrand number with the size of the fuel component being burnt. Hence the ejection height (H) was replaced with $\sqrt{A_s}$, the characteristic length of the component being burnt. The revised non-dimensional firebrand number is given by Equation (9).

$$W^* = \frac{\rho_a}{\mu_\rho} \frac{U_v^2}{g\sqrt{A_s}} \quad (9)$$

Where A_s is the surface area of the fuel exposed to the fire in m^2 from Table 1, ρ_a is the density of air in kg/m^3 in ambient conditions, U_v is the peak vertical ejection velocity in m/s and μ_ρ is the average density of generated firebrands in the wind tunnel experiment in kg/m^3 . For a cedar assembly with gypsum board finish, μ_ρ was 36.4 ± 27.2 kg/m^3 found in Section 3. The non-dimensional firebrand number can be determined for both the wind tunnel (W_{WT}^*) and full-scale (W_{FS}^*) experiments using the conditions in Table 1.

An exploratory data analysis was conducted on the 30 wind tunnel experiments to identify trends applicable to full-scale burning fires. The non-dimensional firebrand number was calculated for these wind tunnel experiments and plotted against a standardised mean of the projected area.

The standardised mean of the projected area was calculated by normalising the mean projected area of firebrands (μ_A), found in Section 3, by the surface area of the burned fuel component (A_S). Noting that 'A' with no subscripts denotes projected area of firebrands. Initial plot analysis suggested a power law relationship: the normalised mean projected area decreased as the non-dimensional firebrand number increased. The power law fitting parameters a and b were determined through least squares fitting of wind tunnel data with the relationship as given by Equation (10).

$$\frac{\mu_A}{A_S} = a * (W^*)^b \quad (10)$$

The absolute errors were determined by the errors between the observed experimental data points and the fitted power law. And the standard deviation of the absolute errors was determined and plotted to give the uncertainty of the power law fit.

With a and b parameters identified, the mean projected area of the full-scale assembly ($\mu_{A,FS}$) can be found with A_S and W_{FS}^* using Equation (10). Note that subscript 'FS' denotes full-scale assembly and 'WT' denotes wind tunnel assembly.

Initially, the upscaled standard deviation was not modelled for simplicity. Instead, a linear scaling factor c, was used to perform the upscale standard deviation shown in Equation (11).

$$\frac{\sigma_A}{A_S} = c \quad (11)$$

However, this simplification led to a log-normal distribution tightly clustered around the mean value, resulting in a normal-like distribution with no significant positive tail, deviating from the findings in Section 3. Therefore, the standard deviation was explicitly modelled for the mass and projected area estimates. Using the error propagation method, the standard deviation (σ) of the predicted quantities can be calculated by propagating the uncertainties of the original quantities through the equations used to derive it.

Observing Equation (9), the W^* equation, only one term contains a standard deviation, the error in the average density of the firebrand estimate (σ_{μ_ρ}), determined from Section 3 for a cedar

assembly with gypsum board finish to be 27.2 kg/m³. Hence, the uncertainty of W^* can be estimated as proportional to uncertainty of μ_ρ by error propagation, given as Equation (12).

$$\sigma_{W^*} = W^* \left(\frac{\sigma_{\mu_\rho}}{\mu_\rho} \right) \quad (12)$$

Uncertainties of $\mu_{A,FS}$ come from a combination of the standard deviations from the parameters a , b , and W_{FS}^* as observed from Equation (10). To propagate the uncertainties from a , b , and W^* , the partial derivatives of $\mu_{A,FS}$ with respect to these parameters were found and given as Equation (13), (14), and (15).

$$\frac{\partial \mu_{A,FS}}{\partial a} = A_{s,FS} \cdot (W_{FS}^*)^b \quad (13) \quad \frac{\partial \mu_{A,FS}}{\partial b} = A_{s,fs} \cdot a \cdot (W_{FS}^*)^b \cdot \ln(W_{FS}^*) \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mu_{A,FS}}{\partial W_{FS}^*} = A_{s,FS} \cdot a \cdot b \cdot (W_{FS}^*)^{b-1} \quad (15)$$

Given the partial derivatives, the standard deviation of the predicted projected area of firebrand ($\sigma_{A,FS}$) can be found using standard deviations with Equation (16).

$$\sigma_{A,FS} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \mu_{A,FS}}{\partial a} \sigma_a \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \mu_{A,FS}}{\partial b} \sigma_b \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \mu_{A,FS}}{\partial W_{FS}^*} \sigma_{W_{FS}^*} \right)^2} \quad (16)$$

4.1.2 Mean Mass Prediction

By assuming constant firebrand density between the upscale, the predicted mean mass of the full-scale assembly firebrand ($\mu_{m,FS}$) can be found by assuming that firebrands are approximately circular in projection. Hence, the mean radius of firebrands ($\mu_{r,FS}$) and the corresponding mean firebrand volume ($\mu_{V,FS}$) in the full-scale assembly can be found by using Equation (17) and (18).

$$\mu_{r,FS} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{A,FS}}{\pi}} \quad (17) \quad \mu_{V,FS} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \mu_{r,FS}^3 \quad (18)$$

Consequently, the predicted mean mass of a firebrand can be found simply with the density equation, given as Equation (19).

$$\mu_{m,FS} = \mu_\rho * \mu_{V,FS} \quad (19)$$

Where μ_ρ is the mean firebrand density of the wind tunnel experiment (36.4 ± 14.5 kg/m³).

The standard deviation of the radius was calculated from the projected area, and the volume of sphere was derived using the cube of radius. Hence the standard deviation of the predicted mean radius ($\sigma_{r,FS}$) and mean volume ($\sigma_{V,FS}$) can be calculated with Equation (20) and (21).

$$\sigma_{r,FS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{A,FS}}{\pi}} \quad (20) \quad \sigma_{V,FS} = \frac{4}{3}\pi(\sigma_{r,FS})^3 \quad (21)$$

Using the error propagation method, the standard deviation of mass ($\sigma_{m,FS}$) is calculated by combining the error in the average density of the firebrand estimate (σ_ρ), and standard deviation of the predicted mean volume, given in Equation (22).

$$\sigma_{m,FS} = \sqrt{(\sigma_\rho^2 \cdot \mu_{V,FS}^2 + \sigma_{V,FS}^2 \cdot \mu_\rho^2 + \sigma_\rho^2 \cdot \sigma_{V,FS}^2)} \quad (22)$$

4.1.3 Bivariate Log Normal Distribution

Using the obtained predicted mean of the mass and projected area, the predicted parameters were transformed into log-normal distribution parameters. The mean (λ) and standard deviation (ζ) parameters of the log-normal distribution can be calculated with Equation (23) and (24), where i denotes the full-scale assembly's predicted mass (m) or projected area (A).

$$\lambda_i = \ln\left(\frac{\mu_i}{\sqrt{1 + \sigma_i^2/\mu_i^2}}\right) \quad (23) \quad \zeta_i = \sqrt{\ln(1 + \sigma_i^2/\mu_i^2)} \quad (24)$$

With two probability distribution parameters of predicted mass and projected area. The interaction between the mass and projected area can be assumed to be the same as the wind tunnel experiment with the Pearson's r coefficient. These can then be combined in a bivariate distribution to generate random samples in the domain, as illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Illustration of a bivariate distribution, adapted from [24]

A covariance matrix (Σ) was constructed using parameters of the log-normal distributions, given as (25).

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_m^2 & \zeta_m \cdot \zeta_A \cdot r \\ r \cdot \zeta_m \cdot \zeta_A & \zeta_A^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

For a cedar assembly with gypsum board finish at 5m/s wind speed, the wind tunnel r coefficient was given as 0.922.

The samples were then randomly generated from the bivariate normal distribution in the log domain with the mean vector and covariance matrix, Equation (26).

$$\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_m \\ \lambda_{A_p} \end{bmatrix}, \Sigma \right) \quad (26)$$

The number of samples generated were determined based on a predicted yield of mass generated from firebrand. This value was less investigated in literature and difficult to validate as full-scale experiments cover a larger area than laboratory set ups, making it challenging to locate and collect all firebrands that are generated. For this analysis, it was proposed that the yield of the wind tunnel assembly (y_{WT}) was scaled with the ratio of non-dimensional firebrand number to obtain a predicted yield of the full-scale (y_{FS}). This was given by Equation (27).

$$y_{FS} = \left(\frac{W^*}{W_{FS}^*} \right) \cdot y_{WT} \quad (27)$$

For a cedar assembly with gypsum board finish at 5m/s wind speed, the wind tunnel yield is 0.0103. The model continues to sample until the yield of masses of firebrands generated reaches the predicted yield value.

As the samples were generated in the log domain, these samples were transformed back to the original scale of mass and projected area by exponentiating, given by Equation (28).

$$Y = \exp(X) \quad (28)$$

4.1.4 Validation

To validate the samples with the observed data points from the full-scale experiment, the samples generated were fitted with a line of best fit with the intercept set to 0, given as Equation (6). Additionally, the maximum and minimum gradient of lines to determine the range of the samples, given as Equation (29), calculated by adding and subtracting the standard deviation of mass to projected area ratio from β , given as Equation (30).

$$\beta_{max} = \beta \pm \sigma\left(\frac{m}{A}\right) \quad (29) \quad \sigma\left(\frac{m}{A}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{m_i}{A_i} - \mu_{\frac{m}{A}}\right)^2} \quad (30)$$

4.2 SCALING RESULTS

4.2.1 Predicted Mean Mass and Mean Projected Area

The result of the non-dimensional firebrand number against the standardised mean projected area is illustrated in Figure 12 showing a weak power law trend. Each individual data point represents a single wind tunnel experiment. The fitted power law curve with parameters a and b is shown in red and the uncertainty range is shown in grey. To ensure the reliability of the fitted parameters, the standard deviations of a and b were used to calculate the 95% confidence intervals. With only 30 samples, the t-distribution was used to determine the confidence interval to account for the additional uncertainty due to the smaller sample size. The parameters a and b are summarised in Table 2.

Figure 12: Dimensionless firebrand parameter against dimensionless mean projected area.

The power law fit shows high variability in a as the standard deviation is close to its estimate, and the lower bound of the confidence interval includes a negative value, which is not physically possible. Despite the variability in a , the estimate of b indicates a statistically significant inverse relationship between the non-dimensional firebrand number and the standardized mean projected area. This supports that the power law fit can capture the relationship between the non-dimensional firebrand number and the standardized mean projected area.

Table 2: Fitted power law parameters.

Parameter	Estimate	Standard Deviation	95% CI Lower Bound	95% CI Upper Bound
a	5.95×10^{-7}	4.58×10^{-7}	0*	1.49×10^{-6}
b	-1.37	0.212	-1.78	-0.948

* The confidence interval is negative but corrected (=0) for a physical parameter

The nondimensional firebrand number for the full-scale assembly was found using the values in Table 1 and Equation (9), found as $(8.95 \pm 4.29) \times 10^{-3}$. This value was notably lower than the range of the laboratory scale experiments shown in Figure 12. By the inverse power law relationship, a larger firebrand projected area was expected. Additionally, the 95% confidence interval includes values that overlapped with the laboratory experiment's lower end. While the

overlap suggests the applicability to extrapolate small-scale data, there could be unknown patterns that the power law is unable to capture. By rearranging Equation (10) and the fitted coefficients in Table 2, the predicted mean of the full-scale assembly ($\mu_{A,fs}$) was found to be $12.6 \pm 11.9 \text{ cm}^2$.

Subsequently, the predicted mean of the projected area was then used to calculate the predicted mean mass ($\mu_{m,fs}$) of the full-scale assembly following methodology from Section 4.1.2, found to be $1.36 \pm 1.56 \text{ g}$.

Both the predicted projected area and mass show significant variability, with the lower bound confidence interval corrected to 0. This reflects the complexity and uncertainty scaling from laboratory scale to full-scale conditions, but also mirrors the high variability in firebrand generation observed in numerous firebrand experiments.

A summary of the full-scale calculated values are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Full scale W^ , predicted mean projected area and mean mass of firebrands*

Parameter	Estimate	Standard Deviation	95% CI Lower Bound	95% CI Upper Bound
W_{FS}^*	8.95×10^{-3}	4.29×10^{-3}	5.49×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-2}
$\mu_{A,FS} \text{ (cm}^2\text{)}$	12.6	11.9	0*	37.0
$\mu_{m,FS} \text{ (g)}$	1.36	1.54	0*	4.51

* The confidence interval is negative but corrected (=0) for a physical parameter

4.2.2 Generation of Firebrand Samples

Firebrand samples were randomly generated from a bivariate log normal distribution, formed with parameters calculated from Table 3 and methodology from Section 4.1.3. The parameters used to form the distribution are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Parameters used in the bivariate log normal distribution.

Parameter	λ_m	λ_A	ζ_m	ζ_A	r
Value	-0.103	0.907	2.21	0.801	0.903

vujfirebrand yield reached the calculated predicted yield of 3.41% from Equation (27). The mean number of firebrands generated with 500 runs was 3981 ± 72 , with percentage difference to the observed firebrand count of 7.2%. Figure 13(a), (b), and (c), shows the final simulation run of results, showing the scatter plot of predicted mass against the predicted projected area and the corresponding distribution. These results were incorporated into the transport model by Gwee et al. [12].

The visualisation of the scatter plot highlights previous findings that a higher number of small firebrands were generated compared to larger firebrands. The distribution plot is right skewed, confirming the properties of a log-normal distribution. Additionally, the range of projected area of firebrands observed in the full-scale assembly was 0.364 – 65.4 cm² (Table 1). The current model had a wider range of 0.113 – 376 cm² after 500 runs. The range of the mass of firebrands was not reported. However, it was roughly estimated from figures reported in Hayashi et al. to be less than 10 g [23], whereas the current model had a wider range of 0.00767 – 68.5 g. This indicated that the firebrand model is predicting a broader spectrum of firebrand sizes.

An explanation for the discrepancy for the larger firebrands not being observed in a full-scale fire than data extrapolated from the wind tunnel experiment may be because extremely large firebrands are unable to be lofted in a fire, and not collected in a full-scale experiment. This will be discussed in Section 5. A summary of the prediction results for the 500 simulation runs was given in Table 5.

Figure 13: (a) Scatter plot of mass vs projected area, (b) Histogram of predicted mass, (c)

Histogram of predicted projected area of the final run

Table 5: Summary of results of full-scale prediction after 500 runs

	y_{FS} [%]	N	σ_N	A_{FS} [cm ²]	m_{FS} [g]
Value	3.412	3981	72	0.113 – 376	0.00767 – 68.5

4.2.3 Model Validation

From the full-scale assembly observed data, Hayashi et al. [23] randomly selected 576 of the collected firebrands to fit a line of best fit of the scatter plot of mass and projected area with the least squares method, shown in Figure 14 (a). The line of best fit from the final simulation of the current model is shown as Figure 14 (b). The slope of the best fit line is 0.114 g/cm², which was close to the observed slope of 0.1054 g/cm² with a positive percentage difference of 8.16%, indicating a good agreement between the observed and predicted firebrands generated. Additionally, the minimum and maximum gradient lines were 0.0679 g/cm² and 0.1544 g/cm², which shows the variability and potential uncertainty in the relationship between the projected area and mass of firebrands. A line with a steeper gradient means that firebrands with the same projected area will have higher masses with higher density. This also poses a greater hazard as such firebrands have a higher ignition potential than smaller firebrands.

The correlation coefficient of the predicted firebrands is 0.874, close to the observed value of 0.914. The percentage difference is 4.38%. This small percentage indicates that the predicted firebrand data closely matches the observed firebrand data.

Figure 14: (a) Scatter plot of full-scale assembly firebrands generated observed (adapted from Hayashi et al. [23]) and (b) predicted (right)

4.2.4 Sensitivity Analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to determine the model performance with hypothetical scenarios. The projected area was selected to be investigated as the methodology of predicted mass also relied on the projected area prediction. The scope of the test was limited to the wind tunnel testing conditions, including varying wind speeds and wall material. Additionally, the surface area of the building was also tested to determine the accuracy of the model. Shown in Figure 15 (a) and (b) are the cumulative distribution function (CDF) plots showing varying wind speeds (5, 14, 23 m/s) with a cedar assembly with a gypsum board finish, and varying materials (cedar, OSB, fibre cement) with 5 m/s wind speed.

Figure 15: CDF plots of predicted projected area (a) varying wind speeds, (b) varying material

Figure 15 (a) demonstrate that the lower wind speed resulted in a steeper gradient of CDF, indicating a more concentrated distribution of smaller projected area firebrands. These firebrands have the same yield as the full-scale scenario in Section 4.2.3, but a lower firebrand count was observed in the higher wind speed due to the larger firebrands generated. Figure 15 (b) show that cedar and OSB generate similarly distributed firebrands, but the fibre cement had the widest spread and larger mean projected area generated. This result is expected as fibre cement materials have a greater density and variance as observed in wind tunnel data analysis.

Shown in Figure 16 is the CDF plot of predicted projected area of firebrands with varying initial surface area exposed to the fire (100, 150, 200, 300 m²) for a cedar assembly at 5 m/s wind speed. The results show that the model will predict firebrands with higher projected areas as the surface area increased. Notably, the 300 m² surface area line is jagged due to the low number of large firebrands that were generated (243). This result was deemed unrealistic as at the cumulative probability of 0.5, deemed as the mean value, the mean projected area was ~ 150 cm² which was 2 times larger than the highest observed experimental mean projected area of a structure (72 cm²), with testing condition also at low wind speed 5.3 – 8.9 m/s [25]. This discrepancy could be due to a combination of the linear scaling of firebrand yield as predicted by Equation (27), and the overprediction of the mean projected area, which resulted in fewer firebrand samples being generated to meet the calculated yield. This also highlights the limit to the size of structure in the

firebrand generation model and reflects the inability of laboratory results to represent larger, full-scale structures.

Figure 16: CDF plot of predicted projected area with varying A_s of building

Additionally, sensitivity of the model to the plume velocity correlation from Tohidi et al. [3] to Himoto et al. [15], given as Equation (2) was investigated. The limitation of Equation (2) was that ejection height was not measured in the small-scale experiment. For this sensitivity analysis, the ejection height of the wind tunnel experiment was assumed to be the height of the structural fuel (0.183 m). Figure 17 shows the comparison of the non-dimensional firebrand number calculated with the plume correlations against the standardised mean of projected area.

The results show that the non-dimensional firebrand number had a significantly higher magnitude and spread for the correlation used in Himoto et al. [15], with the power law trend also observed. However, this led to a 74% change in the mean projected area from the original predicted mean. Although the ejection velocity was estimated in the small-scale assembly, the highlighted the sensitivity of the model to plume velocity correlations. This should be further investigated with more comprehensive firebrand experiments, measuring ejection heights.

Figure 17: Non-dimensional firebrand number against projected calculated with correlations from [3] and [15], showing increase with data calculated with [15].

5 FURTHER DISCUSSION

The model's results align with literature, showing that firebrands generated has a slope of 0.1140 g/cm², with an 8.16% increase when validated against a full-scale experiment. However, there were several limitations in the data used for this model. Firebrands collected in the wind tunnel and full-scale assemblies were post-transport and burning. As discussed in the literature, firebrand reduces its diameter during burning as charring and pyrolysis occurs. For larger firebrands, these may continuously burn during firebrand transport or upon landing causing firebrand size to reduce. For smaller firebrands, they may completely pyrolyze into gas during transport. Hence, size and mass data of firebrands collected post burning had a bias towards smaller and less dense firebrands.

Additionally, the model predicted a greater range of firebrands than the observed data. The discrepancy in prediction can be explained through several reasons. The firebrand generated in a full-scale assembly had an initial fuel surface area significantly greater than in wind tunnel scaled assemblies, which generated larger firebrands. As larger firebrands are denser, it is difficult to be lofted in the wind. These firebrands may remain in the fire or travel extremely short distances that results in the firebrand being burned in the fire and not collected in the experiment.

Additionally, experimental differences exist between wind tunnel and full-scale experiments. For instance, firebrands in wind tunnel tests were quenched with water, while in full-scale assemblies, firebrands were collected post-burning, leading to longer burning times. The wind profile may also differ, as wind barriers exist in larger structures, while wind tunnels have consistent wind profiles. In addition, collecting all firebrands in large-scale assemblies is challenging due to the significantly larger landing area, potentially underestimating the yield of firebrands generated and generate potential bias in the distribution of firebrands. This experimental difference affects the accuracy of characterizing the size and mass of firebrands, which is crucial for the accurate prediction of transport and ignition models.

Furthermore, the model's variability and discrepancy in prediction can also be explained with non-dimensional firebrand number. The power law fit was poor with a high variance due to a small sample size (30 experiments). The terms in the non-dimensional number were calculated from an estimated plume velocity which showed high sensitivity, and the firebrand density was calculated based on a spherical assumption. The spherical assumption does not fully capture the varying sizes and shapes of firebrands. And the transformation of the projected area into volume, and hence upscaling the mean mass required propagation of errors at each transformation. A more robust method of upscaling the mean mass was required from further firebrand experiments to understand physical influences on the firebrand mass.

As found in the literature, FMC was a relevant factor in firebrand generation. These can vary from structure to structure as timber materials is a hygroscopic material that is able to absorb and release water vapour from and to the surrounding air. The model is unable to capture the effects of this as the wind tunnel experiments kept the FMC constant. Moreover, the building experiment was not conducted until structure collapse, while the small-scale experiment does not experience fire contribution from an entire structure. As mentioned in literature, the forces from structural collapse and updraft velocity induced can cause firebrand generation. Hence this methodology was only limited to firebrands generated without the loss of structural integrity. Furthermore, the current model is limited to specific wind speeds (5 m/s, 13 m/s, 22 m/s) and becomes

unstable above a hypothetical 300 m² surface area of fuel, as shown in the sensitivity analysis. This highlights the need for further firebrand experiments.

Assumptions made in this model can be addressed by conducting more laboratory-scale experiments with a comprehensive dataset. In particular, the thickness of firebrands generated, shape, varying fuel moisture content and measuring the ejection velocity of firebrands will be valuable in further development of this model.

6 CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to develop a firebrand generation model that scales laboratory conditions to full-scale conditions and generates data to feed into the firebrand model. The project achieved its objectives through statistical characterization of firebrand mass and projected area, and nondimensionalization. The log-normal distribution was identified as the best fit for firebrand data, effectively capturing the probability distribution of firebrand projected area and mass. Observations indicated that firebrand yield increases with wind speed, consistent with previous studies. The non-dimensional firebrand number demonstrated a power law fit.

In 500 iterations of the model, the number of firebrands generated was predicted to average 3981 ± 72, representing 3.4% of the initial fuel mass. This result showed a 7.2% increase from the observed firebrand count in a previous building fire experiment, indicating reasonable accuracy of the model. Subsequently, these 3981 firebrands were input into a firebrand transport model [12]. The trend of the model aligned well with existing literature. However, the model predicted larger firebrands than observed in the full-scale experiment. This will influence further firebrand hazard predictions as larger firebrands have a higher ignition potential but shorter travel distance.

Additionally, limitations existed in the experimental data, biased towards smaller and less dense as firebrands collected post-transport and burning. Moreover, discrepancies in model predictions could be due to model assumptions relating to burning material, spherical firebrand shape and small sample size of experiments introduced inaccuracies in prediction. Moreover, small-scale

experiments can only partially capture the firebrand generation phenomenon. Therefore, the firebrand generation phenomenon was not fully reflected in the upscaled model.

In conclusion, the developed model demonstrated that upscaling of laboratory results can provide a valuable prediction for full-scale experiments. Further experiments with more comprehensive datasets will significantly improve firebrand generation prediction accuracy and contribute to firebrand transport and ignition models. This work represents an initial step toward better understanding of firebrand generation modelling in structures using deterministic and statistical methods, thereby supporting the enhancement of fire hazard mitigation in urban sites.

AI Assisted writing declaration: I have used ChatGPT to aid in shortening paragraphs. Outputs have not been copy and pasted into this report.

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APPENDIX A

Appendix A Wind Tunnel Assembly Results, raw data from [11]

Cladding	Wall Type	Sheathing Type	Wind Speed (I, M, H)	A [cm ²]	σ_A [cm ²]	λ_A	ζ_A	N	Total Mass [g]	ρ [kg/m ²]	σ_ρ [kg/m ²]	r	β
Cedar	Assembly	Combustible	I	2.43	5.01	1.35	0.944	690	92	36.4	27.2	0.922	0.100
Cedar	Assembly	Combustible	M	2.08	3.71	1.54	0.946	1104	198	36.0	16.5	0.899	0.085
Cedar	Assembly	Combustible	H	3.78	10.78	1.46	0.990	1035	218	40.4	19.4	0.903	0.096
Cedar	Assembly	Non Combustible	I	2.21	2.23	1.28	1.009	465	70	39.8	27.7	0.910	0.111
Cedar	Assembly	Non Combustible	M	2.57	3.44	1.58	0.878	1070	167	35.1	25.5	0.928	0.117
Cedar	Assembly	Non Combustible	H	3.24	6.22	1.73	0.974	994	240	39.5	47.2	0.926	0.090

Cedar	Cladding Only	Non Combustible	I	2.26	3.71	1.48	0.909	497	67	37.3	21.4	0.875	0.114
Cedar	Cladding Only	Non Combustible	M	2.46	3.28	1.58	0.961	814	1085	35.1	15.8	0.887	0.104
Cedar	Cladding Only	Non Combustible	H	3.03	4.67	2.04	0.851	1109	345	50.1	30.9	0.900	0.122
Cedar	Cladding Only	Combustible	I	2.13	2.57	1.10	1.130	537	82	45.2	30.4	0.925	0.094
Cedar	Cladding Only	Combustible	M	2.59	4.30	1.27	0.919	891	225	48.2	29.5	0.939	0.128
Cedar	Cladding Only	Combustible	H	2.82	7.75	1.99	0.988	915	392	48.9	41.1	0.938	0.103
OSB	Assembly	Combustible	I	2.20	4.22	1.42	1.020	559	106	35.0	19.1	0.969	0.122
OSB	Assembly	Combustible	M	2.07	5.99	1.52	1.909	1004	183	35.9	16.4	0.968	0.122
OSB	Assembly	Combustible	H	3.92	7.43	2.25	0.979	1000	350	37.0	18.2	0.918	0.139
OSB	Assembly	Non Combustible	I	2.02	4.14	1.09	1.164	540	45	39.6	17.5	0.968	0.117

OSB	Assembly	Non Combustible	M	2.89	5.29	1.19	1.053	577	107	39.9	20.5	0.969	0.177
OSB	Assembly	Non Combustible	H	3.50	4.95	1.97	0.990	1213	287	39.3	16.8	0.955	0.117
OSB	Cladding Only	Non Combustible	I	2.34	4.47	0.96	1.136	380	56	46.5	20.1	0.961	0.112
OSB	Cladding Only	Non Combustible	M	2.25	3.52	1.41	1.109	776	182	38.0	20.4	0.943	0.113
OSB	Cladding Only	Non Combustible	H	3.64	7.48	2.36	0.833	1131	345	52.8	31.3	0.948	0.154
OSB	Cladding Only	Combustible	I	2.47	3.88	1.21	0.990	516	82	51.3	33.9	0.947	0.125
OSB	Cladding Only	Combustible	M	2.39	3.17	1.02	1.032	857	225	54.6	32.8	0.969	0.124
OSB	Cladding Only	Combustible	H	3.75	5.91	2.29	0.936	999	392	54.8	36.1	0.954	0.140
FC	Assembly	Combustible	I	1.31	2.25	0.75	0.971	452	32	36.6	18.2	0.928	0.109
FC	Assembly	Combustible	M	1.68	2.80	1.10	0.810	870	616	37.1	20.2	0.954	0.106

FC	Assembly	Combustible	H	2.44	2.64	1.70	0.840	1015	168	41.8	31.1	0.891	0.135
FC	Assembly	Non Combustible	I	1.86	2.96	0.99	1.052	364	103	43.5	44.7	0.875	0.153
FC	Assembly	Non Combustible	M	1.63	2.69	0.91	1.002	864	95	50.7	33.8	0.922	0.089
FC	Assembly	Non Combustible	H	3.70	4.99	2.30	0.934	866	650	48.9	25.5	0.931	0.128

- Wind Speed I denotes idle (5 m/s), M denotes medium (14 m/s) and H denotes high (22m/s)
- Sheathing can be combustible or non-combustible

Appendix B

A student who has not used Arial font, font size 11 point, with double line spacing, must copy and paste this page, with its heading, as an appendix to their report. Report markers will use it to verify that the font used has not resulted in a content length advantage for the student. This passage of text fills exactly one page in Arial font, font size 11 point, with double line spacing. In the student's chosen font/format, it must also fill one page or more, but under no circumstances less than one page. This appendix does not count towards the 40-page limit.

Repeat #1: A student who has not used Arial font, font size 11 point, with double line spacing, must copy and paste this page, with its heading, as an appendix to their report. Report markers will use it to verify that the font used has not resulted in a content length advantage for the student. This passage of text fills exactly one page in Arial font, font size 11 point, with double line spacing. In the student's chosen font/format, it must also fill one page or more, but under no circumstances less than one page. This appendix does not count towards the 40-page limit.

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heading, as an appendix to their report. Report markers will use it to verify that the font used has not resulted in a content length advantage. END.